

REMEDICATION OF CRUDE OIL POLLUTED SOIL USING TREATED BIOSOLID (SEWAGE SLUDGE)

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Abstract: This study examines the effect of processed biosolids in the remediation of crude oil contaminated soil. The remediation process was for varying quantities of processed biosolids. The experiment was carried out in Rivers Agricultural Research Institute (RIART) in Rivers State University, Nkpolu, Port-Harcourt. Soil samples with crude oil were in seven (7) reactors (T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅, T₆, T₇) with three replications. The physiochemical properties of the initial soil conditions, processed biosolids Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P), Potassium (K) were analyzed. The physiochemical properties of treated soil such as Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (TPH), Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon (PAH), Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene and Xylene (BTEX), and Bacteria count were analyzed in the laboratory before and after treatment. The result revealed that the contaminated and uncontaminated soils, and biosolids were confirmed loamy sand and grit soils, respectively. The result also showed that the biosolids has high nutrient content of NPK value that is suitable for remediation of contaminated soil. The result similarly indicated that TPH, PAH and BTEX reduced significantly in all the treatment options at the end of the remediation period of 120days. TPH, PAH and BTEX percentage reductions were 99.38, 97.03, and 94.39%, respectively in all treatment options for the period of 120days. In addition, ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) result showed significant difference at 95% confidence levels. It is therefore recommended that the biosolids can be used for degradation of TPH, PAH, and BTEX in crude oil polluted soil.

Keywords: Benzene, Toulene, ethylbenzene, xylene, Biosolid, Crude oil polluted soil, Remediation, Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon, Total petroleum hydrocarbon.

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil is the material basis for the sustainable economic and social development, and is one of the most valuable natural resources in each country. But the excessive presence of chemical elements in regards to their natural content causes soil contamination (Agnello, 2014) and results in a concern and risk to living organisms, human health and overall ecosystem. Soil contamination refers to the presence of toxic chemicals (pollutants or contaminants) in soil in high enough concentrations to pose a risk to human health and/or the ecosystem (Environmental Pollution Centers, 2009). Soil contamination can lead to lack of mineral nutrient, especially nitrogen and phosphorus and this often limits the growth of hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria in water and soil. One of the major contaminants of the soil is crude oil.

Crude oil which is naturally occurring or unrefined petroleum is one of the main sources of energy the world over. Crude oil or petroleum is a complex mixture of hydrocarbons of varying molecular weight and structure. It comprises of three main chemical groups namely paraffinic (aliphatic), naphthenic (alicyclic) and aromatic. These hydrocarbons range from the simple, highly volatile substances to complex waxes and asphaltic compounds which cannot be distilled (Wadley –Smith, 1983; Leahy & Colwell, 1990). Once they enter ecosystems, petroleum-based products initiate a series of processes, affecting both biotic and abiotic elements (Malachowska-Jutz et al., 1997). Crude oil when spilled on land affects the physicochemical properties of the soil such as temperature, structure, nutrient status and pH. Study by Ekemube et al. (2022) revealed that bulk density, total porosity, pH, available P, THC, organic matter, % organic carbon, Total Nitrogen, exchangeable Ca, Na, P, mg, ECEC, TEA, and base saturation were affected due to different volume of crude oil simulated into soil. They also reported that all the characteristics studied including bulk density, pH, available P, THC, organic matter, % organic carbon, total Nitrogen, exchangeable cation (Ca, Na, P, Mg), ECEC, TEA, and base saturation increased with increase in volume of crude oil except porosity. Also, crude oil contamination can impede the normal growth of crops such that it reduces the germination rate and fertility and decline the resistance to pests and diseases (Shan et al., 2014). In addition, the oil compounds could react with inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus limiting the nitrification and removal of phosphoric acid so, the effective nitrogen and phosphorus in the soil would decrease and the absorption of crops will be affected (Pinchin et al., 2013; Liao et al., 2015). Moreover, the polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in petroleum chemicals have carcinogenic, mutagenic, teratogenic and other toxic effects. It can enter into the bodies of people and animals through breathing, skin contact and food degrading the normal function of livers and kidney etc., therefore causing great threat to human's health. Ekemube et al. (2022) found that crude oil alters the physicochemical characteristics of the soil, hence the more the crude oil in the soil the more physicochemical characteristics of soil change thereby causing imbalance in soil nature. Furthermore, their study suggested that remediation should be adopted to regain the originality of the soil. Soil remediation which is sometimes also called soil washing is a process used to treat soils contaminated by heavy metals or other pollutants by removing and changing them into less harmful products. Thus, on site permanent solutions are the preferred method of treatment especially those that involve the complete destruction of the contaminant using biological (natural) techniques, i.e., bioremediation. Bioremediation offers a more environmentally friendly alternative to the degradation of crude oil by taking advantage of oil-degrading microorganisms and by establishing and maintaining the physical, chemical and biological conditions that favour enhanced oil biodegradation rates in the polluted environment (Kanaly & Harayama, 2000; Bento et al., 2005; Sarkar et al., 2005). In the experiment by Agamuthu et al. (2013) demonstrated the effectiveness of organic wastes amended soil and compared it to that of un-mended polluted soil and discovered that Hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria (HUB) counts were 10% higher in all organic wastes amended soil, compared to un-amended control soil throughout the period of study. Ekemube et al. (2021) used organic (spent mushroom substrate - SMS) and inorganic (NPK fertilizer) biostimulants to remediate crude oil

polluted soil, they found that different amount of SMS, NPK fertilizer, and changes in microbial activities were responsible for the removal of total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) concentration across treatment cells. The study of Nduka et al. (2012) demonstrated that the use of fertilizer amendment, the type of microbe, and the type of organic pollutants present influenced the growth of the bacterial population and the efficiency of the contaminant removal. Actually, the amendment contributed to improving the microbial growth, as shown by a tripling in the population size compared to no amendment. Ayotamuno et al. (2006) reported that the total heterotrophic bacterial (THB) counts and a corresponding reduction in soil organic carbon and total hydrocarbon content (THC) at the end of the six-week remediation period. The percentage of THC reduction ranged from 44% to 90% in the five treatment cells.

Biosolid (also known as sewage sludge) is nutrient-rich organic materials resulting from the treatment of domestic sewage in a typical treatment facility. All municipal wastewater treatment plants produce biosolids, which are the stabilized residuals that settle from the water during the various treatment processes. Properly treated and processed sewage sludge becomes biosolids which are nutrient –rich organic materials produced from waste water treatment facilities (Kumar et al., 2016). Application of biosolid (sewage sludge) as a fertilizer on the soil either for plant growth or as a remediation measure for contaminated soil provides a potential way for the effective disposal of sludge. The use of biosolid (sewage sludge) in mitigation and re-vegetation of degraded soil has been shown to be safe to humans and to the environment. Malgorzata et al. (2014) did a column device assessment using contaminated soil from a site surrounding the zinc smelter with a biosolid originating from the food industry for land remediation and the analysis of the biomass confirmed that the used amendment promoted plant growth and significantly increased plant yield. Qin et al. (2012) also revealed that biosolids application on land serve as a beneficial way to recycle organic matter and nutrients, to improve physical, chemical, and biological properties of soils, and to re-establish vegetation and restoration of degraded ecosystem. Chad et al. (2006) observed that biosolids are highly enriched in organic waste contaminants (OWCs) (as mass-normalized concentrations) when compared to effluents or effluent-impacted water. Their results demonstrate the need to better describe the composition and fate of OWCs in biosolids since about 50% of biosolids are land applied and thus become a potentially ubiquitous nonpoint source of OWCs into the environment. Krause et al. (1985), and Linsay and Logan (1998) carried out research on physical properties of soil improved by organic sewage sludge. In a 4years trial with a sandy loamy soil by applying biosolids (2-4% DM content) it was observed that the aggregate size and stability increased with an increased soil organic matter (OM). Grobelak et al. (2017) reported that the single sewage sludge on soil phytoremediation showed that the gradual release of macronutrients from sewage sludge were fully utilized by plants to stimulate their growth and development. Hussein et al. (2010) observed that the application of sewage sludge to the calcareous soil lowered the pH, increases nutritional composition of the soil and electrical conductivity of the soil. Peter et al. (2013) carried out an evaluation using sewage sludge as a sealing layer to remediate sulphidic mine tailings and observed that the sludge was an effective barrier to oxygen influx as it formed both a physical obstruction and

functioned as an organic reactive barrier to prevent oxygen to the underlying tailings. Pierre et al. (2003) suggested that this particular type of activated sludge in their study could be used to increase the efficiency of the treatment of hydrocarbon-contaminated soils in a biopile. Viktorija et al. (2016) did a study on bioremediation of the soil contaminated with petroleum oil products using sewage sludge and observed that diesel fuel was degraded the fastest in samples with KMnO_4 , where efficiency of degradation was 90%, and 88% efficiency in samples with 10% chemical industry plants sludge. They also reported that black oil was degraded the best in samples, where KMnO_4 was added: efficiency of degradation was up to 63%. In the samples with 10% of sewage sludge from chemical industry plant degradation efficiency was 62%. Aboozar et al. (2016) in their study bioremediation of petroleum-contaminated calcareous soil using maize (*Zea Mays L.*) and sewage sludge, revealed the amendments increased root and shoot growth of the experimental plants approximately by a factor of two at the lower sludge treatment level and by a factor of five at the higher sludge treatment level to an immediate stimulation of soil respiration, which then further increased over time. They also opined that sludge treatments also accelerated TPH elimination in the contaminated soil, and again the effect was approximately three times stronger at the higher than at the lower treatment level.

Patrick (2021) conducted a research on remediation of some degraded soils with biosolid of different levels (0.0, 10, 20, ad 30 ton ha⁻¹) on three degraded soil sample. Result showed that composting effects of biosolid reduced pathogen density, odour and conserved the essential nutrients. Biosolid treatment effect significantly reduced the bulk densities and increased total porosity, total N, total organic matter and biomass production ($P < 0.05$) of the three degrade soils. Evanise et al. (2019) observed that addition of wood biochar and sewage sludge-derived biochar to soils led to increased leachate and soil pH. Chua et al. (2006) revealed that maximum oil and grease achieved was 65.6% over the 9 weeks study period under low temperature study condition for the contaminated soil and to sewage sludge of 1:0:5. Bradshaw (1997) observed that Sewage sludge can increase the rate of ecosystem redevelopment, faster than natural succession. Without adequate mineral nutrients, soil organic matter, and mineral particles that keep the ecosystem working and producing new plant material, the ecosystem cannot function (Bradshaw, 1997). Natural succession of ecosystem redevelopment may take a long time to restore to a functional state (Bradshaw, 1997; Palazzo, 1983) as observed in a study of sewage sludge application on infertile and degraded soils, it was seen that sewage sludge increased organic nitrogen and organic carbon levels enough to sustain plant growth where it had not been possible. Their results show that sewage sludge can substantially enhance the remediation of petroleum-contaminated soil, especially when applied in conjunction with a suitable plant such as maize. Theodoratos et al. (2000) investigation on the use of municipal sewage sludge for the stabilization of soil contaminated by mining activities proved that Lead (Pb), Zinc (Zn), and Cadmium (Cd) solubility was reduced by 84%, 64%, and 76% respectively at 15% w/w sewage sludge addition. Vazquez, (2021). Bioaccessibility based in-situ remediation of lead- contaminated soil using local materials such as biosolids, biochar, compost, wood-ash, and soluble phosphorus (SP) amendments have been effective to decrease relative bioavailable (RBA) and in vitro bioaccessibility assays (IVBA)

of lead in soils. Soil sample were incubated for up to 6 Months at constant temperature, moisture and humidity. Phosphorus was the most effective amendment to reduce % IVBA-Pb whether as individual or combined amendments, SP and Biosolids resulted in 25-50% reductions of % IVBA-Pb. Biosolid addition produced, apart from an expected plant available P increase, a great increase in mineralization Nitrogen contents in the soils. Considering the importance of Nitrogen as an essential nutrient in plant growth, these results indicate that this amendment would be suitable for decreasing % IVBA-Pb and overall exposure to Pb contaminated soils. The literature reviews concluded that the biosolids (sewage sludge) is effective in usage for various purposes. It is playing a significant role in energy generation, soil amendment and crop production, etc. The treated biosolid (sewage sludge) which is easy to source locally with little financial outlay will aid in proffering solution for remediation of the crude oil polluted soil for agricultural purposes. Therefore, the aim of this research is evaluating the suitability of biosolid (sewage sludge) for the remediation of crude oil contaminated agricultural soil.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Description of Study Area

The study was conducted at the Rivers Institute of Agriculture and Research Training (RIART) centre located in the Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Port Harcourt is one of the 36 states of Nigeria with its capital at Port Harcourt. Port Harcourt is a vital city positioned within Latitudes 4°45' – 4°60' N and Longitudes 6°55' – 7°56' E (Edokpa & Nwagbara, 2017) on an elevation of 18m above sea level in the Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. The inland part of Rivers state consists of tropical rainforest. Rainy season is from April to November while dry season is from December to March. The ambient environment of Port Harcourt metropolis has a mean monthly relative humidity of 85%, a daily minimum temperature of 23°C and a mean daily maximum temperature of 32°C

2.2 Experimental Materials

The crude oil was gotten from an oil Exploration Company in the area. The sewage sludge (human faecal sludge) was collected from sewer using 20 litres reactors in Port Harcourt Rivers State. The biosolid otherwise known as organic manure was generated and composted for about 3 months and thereafter used for bioremediation of hydrocarbon contaminated soil. The garden soil was collected from University Teaching and Research farm in Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Some other materials and equipment that were used are as follows:

- 1) Plastic containers (referred to as reactors)
- 2) Hand auger
- 3) Hand glove
- 4) Sample bottles for soil collection
- 5) Weigh balance

2.3 Experimental Design

The completely randomized design (CRD) was used in this study. For this experiment, the design consisted of 21 reactors cumulatively for the contaminant source (crude oil). The experimental reactor of volume 0.02 m³ (20 L) which was divided into 7 treatments and 3 replication each totalling 21

reactors each. Each reactor had 5 kg of soil provided for different treatment options They were labelled T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅, T₆, and T₇, including the control T₁ with three replications as shown in Table 1. Randomizations were achieved using the draw lot approach as described in several literatures (Nkakini et al., 2019a; 2019b; Igoni et al., 2019). The experimental design is as follows:

T₁: This is the control without any treatment, 2 times watering per week

T₂: Addition of 200 g of composted sewage sludge (biosolid), 2 times watering per week.

T₃: Addition of 400 g of composted sewage sludge (biosolid), 2 times watering per week.

T₄: Addition of 600 g of composted sewage sludge (biosolid), 2 times watering per week.

T₅: Addition of 800 g of composted sewage sludge (biosolid), 2 times watering per week.

T₆: Addition of 1000 g of composted sewage sludge (biosolid), 2 times watering per week.

T₇: Addition of 1200 g of composted sewage sludge (biosolid), 2 times watering per week.

Table 1: Layout of the Completely Randomize Design for Crude Oil Contaminated Soil

Treatment	Levels of Treatment		
	Replicate 1	Replicate 2	Replicate 3
T ₁	T _{1,1}	T _{1,2}	T _{1,3}
T ₂	T _{2,1}	T _{2,2}	T _{2,3}
T ₃	T _{3,1}	T _{3,2}	T _{3,3}
T ₄	T _{4,1}	T _{4,2}	T _{4,3}
T ₅	T _{5,1}	T _{5,2}	T _{5,3}
T ₆	T _{6,1}	T _{6,2}	T _{6,3}
T ₇	T _{7,1}	T _{7,2}	T _{7,3}

7 Treatments (T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅, T₆, and T₇) Each Replicated Three Times

2.4 Sample Preparation

Soil samples were collected from different random spot per reactor using a hand dug auger capable of obtaining uniform cores of equal volumes to desired depth for the background check. The samples were put in amber coloured glass vials with no headspace to preserve the integrity of the sample in order to prevent volatilization. The sample is then stored in a cooler containing sufficient ice blocks, and transported to the laboratory for analysis in order to achieve background data. The sample preparation was strictly adhered to in line with Environmental Guideline and Standard of petroleum industry in Nigeria (DPR, 2018) for quality assurance. The biosolid (sewage sludge) was composted with sawdust and leaves at the ratio of 10:2:1 (i.e., sewage sludge: sawdust: leaves). The composted sewage sludge was dried totally to such an extent there were no moisture in them. This was done to reduce moisture and gained its contents.

For the experiment, about 5Kg of uncontaminated soil was mixed with sources of crude oil at the ratio equivalent to selected concentrations accordingly. The crude oil sample of 5,000 mg was administered into the each of the 5 kg of soil samples in the reactors through a perforated can. These mixes were in separate reactors for 3 days undisturbed before taken to the laboratory for analysis. On the 3rd day the composted biosolids were added into the contaminated soil at the rates of 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000,

and 1200 g, respectively. Tilling and watering were performed three times a week. Soil samples were also collected from the reactors every two weeks and were taken to the laboratory for analysis.

The properties analysed in the laboratory were total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and BTEX, in crude oil polluted soil respectively on a scale of concentrations in consideration of the DPR (2018) guidelines range of target and intervention values for TPH, PAH, and BTEX.

2.5 TPH, PAH, and BTEX Determination

TPH of the samples were analysed in line with USEPA 8015 method using Gen Tech master G equipped with a split / split less injector, J and W 30-meter DB-5 column and an FID detector. **3.5.3 PAHs.** Also, PAH analysis was carried out in line with EPA 8270 method on an Agilent 6890 GC /MSED 5973 equipped with a split/splitless injector, J and W 30-meter DB-5 column and mass selective detector. **In addition**, a headspace gas chromatographic mass spectrometric (GC-MS) was used for the determination of benzene, toluene ethylbenzene and xylene (BTEX) in soil / water samples.

2.6 Statistical Analysis

A single factor Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significance of the difference in the mean values of each treatment of TPH, PAH and BTEX, respectively, for the various same contaminants during the experiment. This was done based on the F-test. Differences were considered significant if $F_{\text{computed}} > F_{\text{table}}$ at 5% significance levels.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 TPH

The effect of processed biosolids on TPH concentration in the crude oil polluted soil is shown in Table 2. Also, Figure 1 shows the variation of TPH concentration in crude polluted soil with time for different levels of processed biosolids composted on the contaminated soils. An examination of the Figure 1 showed that the TPH concentrations decreased with increase in the quantity of processed biosolids and number of days respectively. The reactors were amended with processed biosolids and water. The TPH concentrations contained in the reactors ranged from 21340 to 131.72 mg/kg for 3, 14, 28, 42, 56 and 70 days, respectively according to the order of reduction. Table 3, shows the percentage reduction of the TPH due to the presence of processed biosolids and microbes' increment. The TPH percentage reductions ranged from 0 to 99.38 % for day 3, 14, 28, 42, 56 and 70, respectively as shown in Figure 2. This might be due to the presence of biosolids introduced to the crude oil polluted soil, which has high content of potassium, moderate quantity of nitrogen, and phosphorus. This is similar to Viktorija et al. (2016) in their study on bioremediation of the soil contaminated with petroleum oil products using sewage sludge and observed that diesel fuel was degraded the fastest in samples with KMnO_4 , where efficiency of degradation was 90%, and 88% efficiency in samples with 10% chemical industry plants sludge. Black oil was degraded the best in samples, where KMnO_4 was added, efficiency of degradation was up to 63% with 10% of sewage sludge from chemical industry plant degradation efficiency was 62%. Also, Aboozar et al. (2016) reported that sewage sludge can substantially enhance the remediation of petroleum-contaminated soil, especially when applied in conjunction with a suitable plant such as

maize. Furthermore, Evanise et al. (2019) carried out research on combining biochar and sewage sludge for immobilization of heavy metals in mining soils, and observed that addition of wood biochar and sewage sludge-derived biochar to soils led to increased leachate and soil pH. Biochar materials were responsible for the greatest reduction of Cd, Pb, and Zn bioavailability. In addition, their study on the use of sewage sludge-derived biochar or the combination of sewage sludge with wood biochar in mining areas are potential alternatives for reusing and aggregating value to these locally available wastes, offering an opportunity to solve both soil remediation and waste disposal problems at once. The addition of biosolids in the treatment options containing huge amount of nutrients that stimulated microbial growth, which led to synthesis of enzymes required to degrade petroleum hydrocarbon compounds (Vidali, 2001). The ANOVA result for the effect of processed biosolid on the TPH concentration showed that there was significant difference in the treatment means at 5% significance levels. This suggests that with 95% confidence, the difference in treatment means was due to the difference processed biosolids applied. This is similar to the findings of Latifa et al. (2018), and Joseph et al. (2020), which revealed that the presence of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in agro-wastes contributed to the high level of degradation of TPH in crude oil contaminated soil.

Table 2: Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (TPH) Laboratory Results

Period (days)	Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon, TPH Concentration (mg/kg)						
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇
3	21340.01	21322.09	21336.01	21331.91	21337.01	21333.61	21335.00
14	18593.59	12388.13	10006.59	8212.79	5974.36	3733.38	1493.45
28	15554.55	7432.88	6003.95	4927.67	3580.62	2240.03	896.07
42	13788.18	5203.02	4202.77	3449.37	2508.43	1568.02	427.25
56	11661.73	3642.11	2941.94	2414.56	1751.90	1097.61	239.07
70	9963.21	1092.63	882.58	724.37	528.57	329.28	131.72

Figure 1: Effect of Processed Biosolids on TPH Contaminated Soil

Table 3: Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon Percentage Reduction

Period (days)	Treatment (%)						
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇
3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
14	12.87	41.90	53.10	61.5	72.00	82.50	93.00
28	27.11	65.14	71.86	76.9	83.22	89.50	95.80
42	35.39	75.60	80.30	83.83	88.24	92.65	98.00
56	45.35	82.92	86.21	88.68	91.79	94.86	98.88
70	53.31	94.88	95.86	96.60	97.52	98.46	99.38

Figure 2: Effect Processed Biosolids on TPH Percentage Reduction in Contaminated Soil

3.2 PAH

The PAH chemical concentration results are presented in Table 4 and graphically presented in Figure 3. The results show that PAH concentrations in the crude oil polluted soil decreased with increase in the quantity of the biosolids introduced. This might be due to the presence of processed biosolids introduced to the crude oil polluted soil as biostimulants, which has high content of potassium, moderate quantity of nitrogen and phosphorus. This is similar to the findings of David et al. (2017); and Eigbuluese et al. (2021) which revealed that agro-waste used as biostimulants enhanced reduction of PAH in crude oil contaminated soil. Their report also revealed that PAH reduction was due to presence of nitrate and phosphate in pineapple peels. The PAH concentrations contained in the reactors

ranged from 168.10 to 1.05 mg/kg for 3, 14, 28, 42, 56 and 70 days, respectively according to the order of reduction. Table 5 shows the percentage reduction of the PAH due to the presence of processed biosolids and microbes' increment. The PAH percentage reductions ranged from 0 to 99.38 % for day 3, 14, 28, 42, 56 and 70, respectively as shown in Figure 4. This is similar to the findings of Evanise et al. (2019) which studied on combining biochar and sewage sludge for immobilization of heavy metals in mining soils, and observed that addition of wood biochar and sewage sludge-derived biochar are potential alternatives for reusing and aggregating value to these locally available wastes, offering an opportunity to solve both soil remediation and waste disposal problems at once. The ANOVA result for the effect of processed biosolids on the PAH concentration showed that there was significant difference in the treatment means at 5 % significance levels. This suggests that with 99 % confidence, the difference in treatment means was due to the quantity of biosolids applied. This finding agrees with the findings of Onakaughtor et al. (2014), and Anna et al. (2016).

Table 4: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon (PAH) Laboratory Results

Period (days)	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon, PAH Concentration (mg/kg)						
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇
3	168.10	164.10	169.21	162.18	170.21	165.61	170.31
14	157.08	95.34	79.36	62.44	47.66	28.98	11.92
28	143.02	57.21	47.62	37.46	28.60	17.39	7.15
42	133.71	40.04	33.33	26.22	20.01	12.17	5.01
56	124.59	28.03	23.33	18.34	14.01	8.52	3.50
70	115.22	8.41	7.00	5.51	4.20	2.56	1.05

Figure 3: Effect of Processed Biosolids on PAH Contaminated Soil

Table 5: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon Percentage Reduction

Period (days)	Treatment (%)						
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇
3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
14	6.56	41.90	53.10	61.50	72.00	82.50	93.00
28	14.92	65.14	71.86	76.90	83.20	89.50	95.8.0
42	20.46	75.60	80.30	83.83	88.24	92.65	97.06
56	25.88	82.92	86.21	88.68	91.77	94.86	97.94
70	31.46	94.88	95.86	96.60	97.53	98.46	99.38

Figure 4: Effect Processed Biosolids on PAH Percentage Reduction in Contaminated Soil

3.3 BTEX

The effect of processed biosolids on BTEX is shown in Table 6. The processed biosolids reduces BTEX in crude oil contaminated soil easily as indicated in Figure 5. This may be due to presence of high content of potassium, moderate nitrogen and phosphorus in processed biosolids. Tilling of the amended soil also increased the aeration that resulted in the degradation of BTEX for the fact that BTEX compounds are very volatile, hence, will readily volatilize in warm/hot climates resulting in higher concentrations in the vapour phase. The BTEX percentage reductions ranged from 0 to 99.38 % for day 3, 14, 28, 42, 56 and 70, respectively as shown in Figure 6 and Table 7. This is in line to the findings of Evanise et al. (2019) which studied on combining biochar and sewage sludge for immobilization of heavy metals in mining soils, and observed that addition of wood biochar and sewage sludge-derived biochar are potential alternatives for reusing and aggregating value to these locally available wastes, offering an opportunity to solve both soil remediation and waste disposal problems at once. The ANOVA result showed that, there were significant difference in the treatment means at 5 % significance levels. This suggests that with 99 % confidence, the difference in treatment means was due

to the processed biosolids applied. This finding agrees with the findings of Onakaughtor et al. (2014), and Anna et al. (2016).

Table 6: BTEX Laboratory Results

Period (days)	BTEX Concentration (mg/kg)						
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇
3	1.62	1.60	1.63	1.62	1.65	1.63	1.64
14	1.53	0.93	0.76	0.62	0.46	0.29	0.11
28	1.48	0.56	0.46	0.37	0.28	0.17	0.07
42	1.38	0.39	0.32	0.26	0.19	0.12	0.05
56	1.28	0.27	0.22	0.18	0.14	0.08	0.03
70	0.90	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.01

Figure 5: Effect of Processed Biosolids on BTEX Contaminated Soil

Table 7: BTEX Percentage Reduction

Period (days)	Treatment (%)						
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇
3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
14	5.44	41.9	53.10	61.5	72.00	82.50	93.00
28	8.82	65.14	71.86	76.9	83.20	89.50	95.80
42	14.57	75.60	80.30	83.83	88.24	92.65	97.06
56	21.00	82.92	86.21	88.68	91.77	94.85	97.94
70	44.39	94.88	95.86	96.60	97.53	98.46	99.38

Figure 6: Effect Processed Biosolids on BTEX Percentage Reduction in Contaminated Soil

4. Conclusions

The appropriateness of processed biosolids for bioremediation of crude oil polluted soil was studied using experimental approach. Test results of the analysis supports the following conclusions:

- i. The uncontaminated, contaminated, and biosolids were confirmed to be loamy sand and grit, respectively, according to United State Department Agriculture (USDA) textural classification of soil.
- ii. Processed biosolids have the potential for remediation of crude oil polluted soil because of their high content of NPK (5.12, 0.85, and 238.74 mg/kg, respectively).
- iii. Processed biosolids influenced the biodegradation of all the parameters (TPH, PAH, BTEX) in the crude oil polluted soil. This is because of its high nutrient composition (NPK). This biosolids degraded TPH, PAH, and BTEX in all treatment were ranged from 31.43 to 99.38% after 70 days of remediation.

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